

COMPUTATIONAL GUIDANCE & NAVIGATION FOR BEARINGS-ONLY RENDEZVOUS – METHODS AND OUTCOMES OF GUIBEAR

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ABSTRACT

GUIBEAR is an activity supported by the European Space Agency aimed at the demonstration of the feasibility of bearings-only (B-O) far-range rendezvous in near rectilinear Halo orbits (NROs). The studied scenario is the far-range rendezvous of the HERACLES Lunar Ascent Element (LAE) with the Lunar Orbital Platform – Gateway (LOP-G) that is orbiting the Moon in an NRO. This activity advances the readiness level of the applicable technologies through a solution based on Computational GNC, structured around a Model Predictive Control framework and tools; and an approach design, development, verification and validation based on iterative prototyping which integrates high-fidelity hosting considerations into the design from a preliminary level: concurrent GNC and software architecture design with hosting, runtime assessment and optical high-fidelity simulations. This paper: presents the context – mission, system and hosting, and algorithm-level challenges and proposed concepts; details and justifies the architecture and design solutions; outlines the methodologies employed for prototyping verification and validation; provides conclusions on the obtained results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Estimating the range to target is the first order challenge of bearings-only rendezvous [1, 2]: the relative position is not instantaneously observable and bearings measurements are nonlinear, which are a source of inconsistency, over-conservatism or divergence of estimates. Observability analysis shows that manoeuvring between at least three non-coplanar (or four coplanar) measurements is necessary to resolve the full relative position and velocity observable. As a result, estimation and control/guidance problems are inherently connected, especially in an autonomous setting. A bearings-only navigation

filter for rendezvous has to cope with the non-linearity of the measurement model and the instantaneous non-observability [3], while including knowledge of manoeuvres through thruster acceleration observables that introduce a significant source of uncertainty. Given all the challenges the navigation filter is exposed to, careful planning of the trajectory in order to maximize the information gain it provides is extremely important. Effectively correcting in closed loop the results of unmodelled dynamics, particularly manoeuvre dispersion and knowledge, favour autonomous on-board guidance functions that present a challenge both in terms of computational load, fuel-cost, estimation performance, and safety. NROs present significantly different orbital environments to existing Earth orbit B-O rendezvous heritage [4, 5, 6]. The nature of the 3-body problem and the absence of complete analytical closed-form solutions are important challenges, but extensive study of this kind of orbits shows that, for the scenarios considered and short timescales, closed-form approximations are applicable. The distances introduce significant challenges on target detection and tracking as the target is at sub-pixel resolution, such as increased exposure times. This purely radiometric detection relies on the capability of disentangling the target contribution to the pixel readout from the background contribution due to cosmic background radiation (diffuse sky emission), background signals, and to instrument noise itself. Aside from these challenges in terms of the main sensor in the considered suite, several other hosting challenges are present. For example, effectively measuring the executed delta-V is also a relevant challenge, given that accelerometers are perturbed by various different error sources, from drifting biases to multiplicative cross-coupling errors. Finally, the online nature of the GNC solution also presents significant challenges in terms of runtime constraints and processing architectures. The on-board computational power has to be able to solve the constrained optimization problem that underlies the guidance function in real time.

The GUIBEAR study aims at addressing all these challenges, through the design of an algorithmic or computational Guidance and Navigation architecture. The computational efficiency, accuracy and robustness of the trajectory generation are at the foundation of the design, as the numerical generation of guidance commands relies extensively on on-board computation. The autonomous guidance function is based on an optimization problem with the objective of 1) maximizing the observability of the range and 2) minimizing the fuel consumption. This optimization problem bridges the gap between estimation and control, thus approaching the potential of a truly autonomous system: the navigation filter informs the computation of the trajectory, which in turn is optimized to improve the navigation performance. In order to close the loop, the optimization problem is solved online, and its solution is updated whenever the uncertainty of the navigation filter decreases. Adding the capability to enforce input (saturation, maximum ΔV , minimum acceleration necessary for detection) and output (safety and final conditions) constraints to the optimization of the performance index lead to the formulation of the multi-objective optimization problem in a model predictive control (MPC) framework [7]. Ultimately, this provides a process to reduce the navigation errors systematically throughout the mission, while taking advantage of this same reduction to improve the commanded plan. The bearings-only estimation filter is tailored for monocular vision-based navigation, taking into account the particularities of the NRO environment and the difficulties of navigating when the target is always at sub-pixel resolution. For that purpose, a weighted least squares batch estimator is employed, improving the accuracy and outlier rejection while dealing with such challenges as varying camera integration times and computational cost. This filter is complemented by a higher frequency state estimator that not only propagates the dynamics whenever measurements are not available, but also combines the higher quality information provided by the batch filter. The resulting architecture is then a mixture of sequential and batch processing, and consequently high and low frequency processing tasks. Since accurate navigation is only necessary before the computation of the next guidance profile by the MPC, this exploits the structure of the mission scenario with the objective of improving the navigation perfor-

mance, as it minimizes sensor measurement errors, saves computational time, and minimizes the real time operational constraints. The proposed Computational G&N architecture is verified and validated in simulation, taking as baseline the studied scenario. The LAE launches from the Moon, and ascends to an elliptical low Moon Orbit, which is circularized into a circular low Moon orbit. This is followed by an orbit transfer and phasing phase that place inject the LAE in free drift at which point it is able to detect the target from a distance larger than 1000 km. The scenario tackled in this activity is the approach and autonomous injection of the LAE in the LOP-G's NRO, leaving the former in handover conditions for the start of rendezvous proper, at 100 km from the latter.

The feasibility of performing far approach through these mass and cost-saving camera-only GNC techniques is established and justified through prototyping and extensive testing in Model-In-The-Loop high-fidelity simulations. Autocoding and Software-In-The-Loop testing are performed as a bridging step towards the subsequent phases of the V&V process – laboratorial Hardware-In-The-Loop campaigns. As part of the strategy a novel method employed for benchmarking of runtime of the auto-coded software is described: preliminary non-realtime PIL assessment employed at algorithm development level. This method includes a step of experimental compilation and running of a segment with a number of GNC cycles in a flight-representative processor thus allowing adjusting GNC parameters and runtime latency emulation blocks in the functional simulator.

2 THE GUIBEAR PROJECT

The GUIBEAR project is a natural extension of the NRO-GNC project [5], in the sense that it builds on the DDVV process therein, and is focused on the final part of the Orbit transfer phase, particularly up to and including the NRO insertion manoeuvre as noted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: LAE mission scenario, with the phases of interest highlighted in dark red: the ascent/circularization and LLO loitering phases; in red: the orbit transfer phase; and in grey: the rendezvous phase. On the right, the very far range nominal scenario. In red the trajectory of the chaser from the LLO to the NRO. In blue, the target trajectory.

2.1 Timeline

The baseline approach uses an orbital transfer from low-lunar orbit (100 km altitude) to the halo orbit (approximately 7000 x 70000 km altitude) that consists of two impulsive manoeuvres plus a mid-course correction (for a total of 3 manoeuvres). The orbit transfer from low-lunar orbit starts

with a transfer injection manoeuvre and ends with an NRO insertion manoeuvre. The manoeuvres are computed as two-impulse transfers analogous to the Lambert problem in central-body / Keplerian dynamics. That is to say, the manoeuvres are computed deterministically, taking into account the three-body dynamics in an ephemeris model of the Earth-Moon system. Relative observations can start during the free drift prior to the NRO insertion manoeuvre (IM).

Towards the end of the transfer the navigation will switch from a ground-based tracking solution to a camera based navigation solution. The handover from ground tracking to the camera sensor based navigation is planned to occur at a distance of 1000 to 1500 km distance from the LOP-G station. The handover conditions are mainly determined by the accuracy of the ground tracking and the illumination conditions at the time of the handover.

2.2 Scenarios

Three scenarios are defined where the initial conditions for all scenarios are the same. The scenarios all start 20 hours before the nominal NRO insertion manoeuvre occurs, at a distance of 1500 km from the LOP-G. The terminal conditions for all scenarios should be the same: to arrive at the hold point at 150 km 20 hours after the start of the scenario. Note that in all scenarios some time is included after the insertion manoeuvre for relative observations, in order to leverage the range observation enhancement opportunity provided by the insertion manoeuvre itself. The three scenarios considered are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: GUIBEAR Scenarios.

Scenario 1 (Baseline)	This scenario is used to evaluate how well range can be observed without performing additional manoeuvres. This includes a scenario with pre-planned insertion (PI) and online-computed insertion (OI).
Scenario 2 (Insertion untouched)	MPC based observation enhancing manoeuvres are being performed, but the insertion is performed as planned in the baseline.
Scenario 3 (Full MPC)	All manoeuvres, including the insertion, are recomputed using MPC. Fuel-optimal (F) and Observability-optimal (O) cases are addressed.

The baseline scenario is essentially the same as the Heracles LAE scenario as described in [5]. This scenario consists of a single manoeuvre taking place, the NRO insertion manoeuvre. This manoeuvre has a nominal ΔV of 20 m/s. Two observations performed before and two observations performed after a manoeuvre make the camera based navigation problem fully observable. This means that even if no additional manoeuvres are planned, the fact that the NRO insertion manoeuvre needs to be performed would already provide an opportunity for making the problem observable (that is, by taking at least two directional measurements before and after performing the NRO insertion manoeuvre). This is considered the baseline scenario. In the second scenario, manoeuvres are added before the insertion manoeuvre, but the insertion manoeuvre itself is left untouched by the MPC. This implies that the additional manoeuvres are small (of the order of 1 m/s), and that at the end of the sequence of additional manoeuvres the LAE is in the correct position to perform the insertion manoeuvre. The computation of the insertion manoeuvre takes into account the improved navigation available through the sequence of manoeuvres. In practice this means that the timing of the manoeuvre can be adjusted on-board based on the relative navigation to ensure the LAE arrives at the hold point. Ideally, the sequence of manoeuvres should not greatly increase the uncertainty in position with respect to the estimated ground tracking based accuracy (that is, 6 km on all axes) if no measurements would be taken. In this way, the observability enhancement manoeuvres could be performed without interfering

with the nominal operations defined in the baseline approach. In the third scenario, the MPC generates a sequence of manoeuvres that include the insertion into the hold point at 150 km. The only restrictions are as stated above, namely, that the scenario ends 20 hours after the nominal starting point at a distance of 1500 km and that the ΔV is less than a maximum that includes the ΔV of the insertion manoeuvre and a margin for observability enhancements. In this scenario the MPC has the most freedom to design the trajectory and can work with larger manoeuvres than the other two scenarios.

3 GUIBEAR G&N DESIGN

In a classical sequential architecture, the loop starts acquiring data from the available sensor suite; the measurements are then processed by a sequential Navigation Filter that at each time instant provides a state vector estimation - when no measurements are available the filter will only propagate the dynamic model implemented. Using the covariance measurement it is possible to determine if the accuracy has substantially improved from the past. If the accuracy has improved substantially from the last execution of the guidance computation, the guidance function is executed. The guidance function can also be executed periodically and in case the Navigation accuracy has not improved from the past execution the guidance call is aborted. The guidance function computes the entire trajectory and it is used in the high frequency cycle. On a different flavour, the G&N architecture designed in GUIBEAR includes a mix of sequential processing and batch processing, and consequently High frequency and Low frequency processing tasks. The high frequency tasks consists as first task collecting data from samples as it was described for the previous architecture. The second task consists in estimating the state vector using a simple algorithm as for example simple propagator of the dynamics, something that in the previous architecture is also performed when measurements are not available. Knowing the trajectory, it is possible to know if the manoeuvre has to be applied within the current cycle, if yes the control applies the manoeuvre. In parallel, there are Low Frequency processes running that can be synchronized with the mission trajectory. The sensors measurements are collected in data batch and processed within a Navigation Filtering which uses batch filtering with dynamic models and measurements collected at different time. The Navigation provides an estimation of the performed arc averaging all the measurement errors of the collected data. More accurate dynamical models can be

Figure 2: The G&N architecture designed during the activity: mixed batch and sequential processing. On the right, low frequency tasks execution proposed concepts overlapped over the trajectory

used since there is not a stringent requirement on the navigation frequency but especially the batch

filtering is a simple method for reducing the measurement noise while fitting the trajectory. Once the navigation solution is computed, the information is passed to the State vector estimator of the High frequency task in order to use as soon as possible the most update information. If the accuracy has improved substantially from the last execution of the guidance computation, the guidance function is called. Alternatively the guidance function can be also executed periodically and in case the Navigation accuracy has not improved from the past execution the guidance call is aborted. As in the sequential case, the Guidance when executed generates an entire trajectory that updates the existing trajectory. This strategy fits very well in the mission scenario, since accurate navigation solution is only needed before the execution of the manoeuvres and this time can be foreseen since the trajectory is known up to the end. Consequently, knowing the time needed for executing the Navigation Filtering and the guidance functions, it can be planned measurement data collection between 2 manoeuvres in order to have the navigation solution and possibly a re-computation of the trajectory before the following manoeuvre. The described concept is depicted in the right-hand side of Figure 2 reporting the time dedicated to collect data, Navigation Filtering Execution and Guidance Execution over the trajectory. This solution provides better performance because it minimizes sensors measurement errors through a batch filtering process also saving computational time since the on-board computer (OBC) is extensively used only when Navigation and Guidance are executed. Furthermore, it minimizes the real time constraints of the Navigation since the only constraints is that Navigation and guidance are executed before the next manoeuvres. The time between manoeuvres is set *a priori* and drives the prediction model used on the optimization-based guidance.

3.1 Guidance

In general, a line-of-sight measurement profile is unique when, given an observation period, it can only be generated by one possible trajectory. For different relative trajectories, there may be periods with the same azimuth and elevation readings, but for the entirety of the observations the overall measurement profile must be unique. Since the measurement profile can be identified with the initial conditions, a unique profile and the associated motion are associated with uniquely determining the initial conditions. When that is possible, the system is observable. This is the topic of several works on bearings-only rendezvous in LEO (see [8] and [9]). To apply this concept in the context of an NRO, it should be noted that the last segment of the transfer from LLO to halo covers a small fraction of the orbital period, such that the dynamics is very slow. Furthermore, the chaser moves along a trajectory that is nearly a straight line. This means that dynamical coupling of the axes is quite weak. By contrast, the motion in the x and z directions of the LVLH frame are dynamically coupled in the case of LEO rendezvous. These considerations can inform a geometrical observability analysis that itself can steer the trajectory design. Some conclusions are: (i) Maximizing observability of a manoeuvre requires that it is performed perpendicular to the direction of the target; (ii) Observability is fostered by changes in observation angle and the angular momentum. The former are maximized when the manoeuvre is perpendicular to the angular momentum and the direction to the target, and the latter when it is collinear with the angular momentum; Taken together, these recommendations point to a guidance strategy in which manoeuvres are performed such that the trajectory resembles a 3-dimensional spiral.

By deriving the observability Gramian for the bearings-only navigation problem, it is possible to add further considerations to the G&N design: (i) If the spacecraft moves perpendicularly to the original direction to the target twice, three different measurements will provide observability, otherwise at least four measurements are necessary; (ii) Some manoeuvres may not provide observability if the measurement profile does not change, i.e., if the new position lies in the same direction to the target as it would without manoeuvres.

3.1.1 Observability-enhancing Guidance

In fully observable frameworks, the problem of deciding how to move is typically decoupled from the estimation problem. However, in situations where motion can critically assist the observability, or indeed be a necessary condition, it is beneficial to consider the two problems together. [10], [11], [12], and [13] explore strategies for trajectories that enhance the observability of the problem, and hence, the performance of the related estimation algorithms. Some of these works are based on geometric considerations, and provide particular trajectories that can improve or guarantee the observability of the manoeuvre. For example, [12] addresses the possibility of using spiralling trajectories and hints at their interesting properties in terms of estimation performance. However, a formal understanding and design of trajectories is not presented. [10], on the other hand, is focused on establishing the concept of “observability degree” and derive a metric for the range estimation error related to the actual distance, the angular difference between the trajectory with and without manoeuvre, and the measurement error. Their next step is to use this metric as a cost function in a minimization problem that is solved analytically for an impulsive manoeuvre and provides interesting insight into the optimal trajectories. In the context of a real mission, these approaches are very interesting as stepping stones, but when considering operational constraints the solution of such an optimization problem becomes more complex. Not only are nonlinear non-convex problems harder to solve, an on-board solution needs to be solvable fast and deterministically. Therefore, the optimization problem is transcribed in order to result in a convex QP problem, since linear or quadratic optimization problems are guaranteed to be solvable in a finite and possibly known number of iterations [14]. The approach proposed in [13], is to obtain a discretized trajectory in n steps, with n possible inputs, which allows for quadratic programming. The resulting optimization variables are the relative states in all steps, the controls, and slack variables used to encode the norm constraints linearly. The constraints considered are the discrete relative motion dynamics (discretized from analytically integrating the Clohessy-Wiltshire equations, applicable only to circular orbits), boundary conditions (initial and final state), thruster saturation, and manoeuvre objectives (approach corridors, collision avoidance). When the optimization problem is convex, it allows to correct the rendezvous planning multiple times along the trajectory. This is, in fact, similar to model predictive control schemes with dynamic avoidance constraints. Bridging this approach to the typical MPC scheme, it should be noted that the typical receding time horizon is replaced by a fixed final set point, shrinking the time horizon accordingly. This approach to the design of a guidance function has a natural formulation as a trajectory optimization problem with a fixed-horizon. An online computation (on-board or ground-based) of the trajectory that is updated every time step according to the current knowledge provided by the estimation filter and taking into account eventual errors in previous manoeuvres. Noting that the optimization problem is updated every step, and only the first manoeuvre is executed before a new plan is optimized, this guidance function fits directly in the Model Predictive Control area, noting that the last step of optimization is fixed instead of receding, and the horizon is shrinking.

Cost function The cost function to be considered has two main terms, an actuation cost and an observability cost. The former is

$$J_f = \sum_{k=0}^{N(t)-1} \mathbf{1}^T |\mathbf{u}_k| \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is a vector of ones used to sum the absolute values of each input. The observability cost is based on the work in [9] and [13]. These costs proposed are not convex, and, as such, are convexified by means of slack variables and previous trajectory information. Furthermore, it became clear during the activity that the above observability cost does not correlate perfectly with the observability

of the range, instead being replaced by the angle between the would-be trajectory and the actual one (or its cosine, in fact):

$$J_o = \sum_{k=0}^{N(t)-1} \frac{\mathbf{x}_k \Phi^T(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S} (\Phi(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{G}(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{u}_k)}{\|\Phi(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{x}_k\| \|\mathbf{S} (\Phi(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{G}(t_{k+1}, t_k) \mathbf{u}_k)\|} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{S} selects the relative position component.

Dynamic model The propagation methods analysed for GUIBEAR can be separated into numerical non-linear propagation and linearized propagation. The baseline trajectories of chaser and target have been obtained through a numerical integration of the equations of motion. These equations include central forces from the gravity of the Earth and the Moon:

$$\mathbf{a}_{SC} = -\frac{GM_{Earth}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{SC-Earth}\|^3} \mathbf{r}_{SC-Earth} - \frac{GM_{Moon}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{SC-Moon}\|^3} \mathbf{r}_{SC-Moon} \quad (3)$$

Expressed as the 6 first order differential equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{SC} \\ \dot{\mathbf{v}}_{SC} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{v}_{SC}, \mathbf{a}_{SC}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_{SC} \\ \mathbf{a}_{SC} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

This propagation method considers an inertial frame centred at the Earth-Moon barycentre that is parallel to J2000. The position of the Earth and the Moon is obtained through an ephemeris model of the two bodies (from JPL ephemeris). The initial conditions of the Target (which follows an NRO) is obtained through a process of differential correction to obtain a semi-stable trajectory, whereas the chaser trajectory is obtained through mission analysis. Both the differential correction process and the mission analysis are detailed in [5, 6]. The trajectories obtained through this numerical integration are considered the reference trajectories, and the different linearized methods are compared to these references. The trajectory of the target is considered as reference, and the trajectory of the chaser is a deviation with respect to the reference. The method chosen is based on a computation of the state transition matrix (STM), which maps an initial state $\mathbf{0}$ to a final state \mathbf{f} as:

$$\mathbf{x}_f = \Phi(t_f, t_0) \mathbf{x}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi^{rr}(t_f, t_0) & \Phi^{rv}(t_f, t_0) \\ \Phi^{vr}(t_f, t_0) & \Phi^{vv}(t_f, t_0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_0 \\ \mathbf{v}_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

which can be obtained as a solution to the system

$$\dot{\Phi}(t, t_0) = \underbrace{\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}}}_{\mathbf{A}(t)} \Phi(t, t_0), \quad \Phi(t_0, t_0) = \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

The approach consists on integrating the system (6) numerically. The matrix $\mathbf{A}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is evaluated at each point in time using the reference trajectory of the target.

While the numerical propagation of the STM seems expensive at first, the computation of the STM depends only on the trajectory of the target, the Moon and the Earth. These three elements are known a priori on ground, so it is possible to propagate the STM numerically on ground for an arbitrarily large interval (e.g. one NRO period, or a few days around the aposelene), perform a fitting of the STM coefficients on ground and then sending/storing them on the OBSW. With this approach, the STM would be obtained in a similar way as planetary ephemeris are used, requiring a small number of operations to evaluate a polynomial. Analysis results show that a fitting using polynomials of order 6 to 8 provide results that are good for the applications proposed. Furthermore, it could be possible to obtain the STM between any given interval by applying STM composition rules (generally requiring the evaluation of 2 STM and inverting one of them).

Constraints The (convex) constraints considered in the guidance design are (i) maximum delta-V per manoeuvre; (ii) total delta-V budget; (iii) target rendezvous sphere avoidance; (iv) escape trajectory avoidance; and (v) passive safe trajectory enforcement.

Model Predictive Control Within the GUIBEAR project, the software tool MPCSoft developed during the project “ROBMPC – Robust model predictive control of space constrained systems” (2010-2012) has been modified to support the features needed to formulate and solve the MPC problem proposed above to control far-range bearings-only rendezvous in NRO. The original implementation of the toolbox MPCSoft lacked some of the features needed to handle the peculiarities of the MPC problems arising in the context of the GUIBEAR scenarios. Specifically, such peculiarities consist in the presence in the cost function of: (i) a linear term, aimed at minimizing fuel consumption, (ii) a positive semidefinite quadratic term, aimed at enhancing the observability of the trajectory, that may render the problem not strictly convex. In order to overcome these limitations, some improvements to the toolbox have been carried out and the current MPC formulation supported by the toolbox has been modified to enable the user to minimize linear terms in the cost function.

The LTV-MPC toolbox MPCSoft2.0 relies on a Simulink Library that includes a block for LTV-MPC, implementing the controller in Embedded MATLAB (EML). MPCSoft used to be interfaced to the QP solver that was available from the MPC Toolbox for MATLAB in 2010. Such QP solver was based on rather classical active-set methods for strictly convex QPs, and therefore appeared not tailored to address the solution of QP problems such as those arising in the GUIBEAR scenarios, in which, due to the observability-enhancing cost, the Hessian matrix is positive semidefinite. In order to overcome this issue, MPCSoft2.0 was interfaced to two more recent QP solvers, both based on the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) [15] namely: (i) a QP solver internally developed at ODYS, that implements the ADMM in EML and is therefore tailored for code generation, (ii) the open-source solver osQP [16], which is called by MPCSoft2.0 through its MATLAB interface.

3.2 Navigation

The developed Navigation algorithm is based on batch filtering that processes Image Processing measurements and, in between filter updates, it propagates the translational states based on the dynamics model. The approach followed has resulted in a very efficient method since the batch filtering is less sensible to measurement noise due to the fact that a large number of measurements are used to fit the relative dynamics. On the other hand, as the Image Processing is the only relative sensor, it is certainly understandable that the Navigation performance is highly connected to the Image Processing performances and measurement availability. Within GUIBEAR, the approach followed has been to implement an Image Processing Performance Model to mimic the behaviour of the IP algorithms both in the measurements performance and the availability in function of the distance and the angular velocity of the object within the camera frame. Indeed, based on a camera model implemented in PANGU [17] and tuned with respect to the parameters of the selected camera, different synthetic images have been generated. The different synthetic images are used to build an Image dataset, which then serves as input to the real Image Processing algorithm (IP Functional Model). The outputs of the IP functional models have been statistically analysed in order to derive the performance of the measurements and the probability of providing measurements of the IP algorithms. The estimated statistical quantities have been used to derive the IP performance model that is integrated in the Functional Engineering Simulator (FES) together with the GNC algorithms.

This section includes a summary of the batch processor algorithm used in the state estimation. The summary includes a general description of the algorithm, plus specific points that apply to the GUIBEAR scenario. A more detailed mathematical description and derivation of the algorithm is included

in [18].

3.2.1 Batch filter

The objective is to estimate a deviation vector \mathbf{x}_0 at a reference time t_0 . The information provided is the initial condition $\mathbf{x}(t_0)$, an *a priori* estimate of the initial condition $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_0$ and its associated covariance matrix $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_0^-$. An estimate of the deviation vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ is obtained solving the normal equation

$$\Lambda_0 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{y} + \bar{\mathbf{P}}_0^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{x}}_0, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t_i), t_i)$ is the measurement vector, \mathbf{R} is the measurement covariance, Λ_0 is the information matrix, given by

$$\Lambda_0 = \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \bar{\mathbf{P}}_0^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

and \mathbf{H} is the observation-state mapping matrix, evaluated at the reference trajectory mapped to the reference time, as in

$$\mathbf{H}_i = \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t_i), t_i)}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \Phi(t_i, t_0). \quad (9)$$

In this activity, the observation transformation $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t_i), t_i)$ is defined as a projection of the target state vector in camera frame, scaled with the camera focal length.

The measurement noise covariance is considered as a diagonal matrix for each measurement, with value $\mathbf{R} = \sigma_{px}^2 \mathbf{I}$, where σ_{px}^2 is the variance of the measurement noise, considered constant for every measurement.

The state propagation is performed by linearly mapping a state vector from a reference time to a time i using the state transition matrix. The state vector at a time i is a linear combination of the state vector at the reference time, plus the effect of each manoeuvre, mapped from manoeuvre time to time i :

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \Phi(t_i, t_0) \mathbf{x}_0 + \sum_{n=1}^m \Phi(t_i, t_n) \Delta \mathbf{v}_n \quad (10)$$

The state transition matrix defined depends on the trajectory of the target, it is not modified by the manoeuvres and only depends on the initial and final times. Because of that, the state propagation can be arranged into a single matrix product with an augmented state transition matrix and an augmented state vector, $\mathbf{x}_i = \bar{\Phi}^*(t_i, t_0) \mathbf{X}_0^* = [\Phi(t_i, t_0) \quad \Phi(t_i, t_m) \quad \dots \quad \Phi(t_i, t_1)] [\mathbf{x}_0^T \quad \Delta \mathbf{v}_m^T \quad \dots \quad \Delta \mathbf{v}_1^T]^T$. Since the reference trajectory is propagated linearly, both the reference and the deviation with respect to the reference are propagated using the same approach. Finally, the *a priori* covariance is obtained for the augmented state vector using the ground tracking estimate and an estimation of the manoeuvre execution. $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_0 = \text{diag}(\sigma_{x_0}^2 \mathbf{I}, \sigma_{\Delta v}^2 \mathbf{I})$.

3.2.2 Analysis

During the activity, an analysis and trade-off of bearings-only navigation approaches based on the batch least-squares processor described above was performed. The first objective was to define a measurement strategy, i.e. number and distribution of measurements, considering the relevant parameters of the problem, which are enumerated and defined below. The second objective was to understand the impact of each parameter in the solution obtained, which can be used as an iteration with the requirements. In summary, the navigation strategy should consider the following conclusions:

- Both manoeuvre size and manoeuvre estimation are important parameters when improving the radial component estimation. A budget of the order of 20 m/s could provide solutions with

a standard deviation of the initial condition of 3 km, but this budget is only accessible if the MPC has control over the insertion manoeuvre. To reduce the number of manoeuvres, each manoeuvre needs to have a value of at least 1 m/s. The manoeuvre estimation error needs to be of the order of 1 cm/s, but the combination of larger manoeuvres and smaller errors has not been analysed in detail, a preliminary limit of manoeuvre estimation error is set to 1%.

- It would be necessary to rely on a more accurate propagation and estimation of the state transition matrix to improve the solutions and benefit from smaller manoeuvre estimation errors. Considering the current navigation errors and the navigation objective, this update does not seem necessary at this moment.
- Several successive measurements can be used to improve the solution, which have the effect of reducing the measurement noise. If the measurement noise was reduced, the number of measurements could be reduced. However, to be compatible with conservative values ($1 \text{ px } 3\sigma$), 3 to 5 measurements seem to be enough.
- Distancing the measurement to increase the change in angle optimizes the measurement placement.
- The current values for ground tracking estimation errors (6 km, 12 cm/s, 1σ), in combination with the rest of uncertainties using conservative values, produce solutions that have a position error of 0.4 % with respect to the distance and a velocity error of 0.4% with respect to the relative velocity. It was expected to maintain the percentage over the entire scenario, obtaining Navigation error improved of 1 order of magnitude with respect to the error considered without GUIBEAR.
- The current combination of noise and parameters appears to be robust to large uncertainties.

4 SIMULATION RESULTS

The main objective of the GUIBEAR G&N system is to ensure that the mission vehicle arrives at the hold point (HP) within the specified area and performs the insertion manoeuvre successfully. The G&N must tackle the optimization objectives and constraints while dealing with uncertainty in some parameters in the system, sensor noise, and external disturbances. Given the closed-loop nature of the guidance function the DDVV process has some similarities to the design of a control system, including the synthesis and first analysis of the G&N functions. However, the performance assessment is done by means of a SW Functional Engineering Simulator (FES). The FES for detailed performance assessment contains high fidelity models that are non-linear, in general. Additionally, other aspects of the mission such as the Mission & Vehicle Management functions and the mode transition logic can be considered. In this phase, the G&N performance was evaluated against specific mission requirements, defined in the mission domain (e.g. fulfilment of HP requirement or fuel consumed).

Figures 3 and 4 show the nominal navigation performance of the two MPC-based scenarios, and table 2 allows to compare the three main scenarios statistically (and which can be directly compared, as the insertion is based on on-board navigation for all three). From this analysis, it is clear that the introduction of observability-enhancing manoeuvres has a beneficial effect. Furthermore, the fully optimized Scenario 3 shows the best performance, as expected.

The comparison in tables 3 and 4 again shows the good performance of the overall G&N, as it allows reducing the position and velocity dispersion when compared to the online planned insertion with no guidance. This reduction has a significant impact, because it will not only allow a better planning

Figure 3: Navigation results for Scenario 2.

Figure 4: Navigation results for Scenario 3.

of the rendezvous, but also a reduction on delta-V spent to correct for it. This fact, allowed with the significantly improved knowledge of the relative state can lead to a less strict mission analysis plan, allowing the rendezvous to start closer to the target, again reducing delta-V expenditure as seen in table 5.

The delta-V budget allocated for the GUIBEAR approach is, naturally, constrained by the mission analysis and the end-to-end results of NRO-GNC [5]. It is clear that the considerations of that activity did not take into account the possibility of performing an on-board optimized trajectory to approach the hold point for preparation of the rendezvous, nor the existence of a long range navigation function that could improve on the costly and infrequent ground estimates. For that reason, the insertion manoeuvre was planned with a large dispersion in mind, stemming from the TCM. With GUIBEAR, it is not only possible to have a bearings-only navigation that provides timely estimates of the relative position and velocity of the target, but also to plan the trajectories taking into account these. This comes, naturally, at a cost of delta-V but not of extra sensors. The analysis present in this paper shows that a very small delta-V budget dedicated for observability-enhancing manoeuvres does help the navigation performance and the observability, but its influence is limited. However, larger manoeuvres

Table 2: Statistical results of the Range Estimation Error before the NIM for the main cases.

Range Estimation	Scenario 1-OI	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Metric:	5%	5%	5%
Mean:	9.7462%	1.2624%	1.1874%
Std. Deviation:	17.708%	1.2424%	1.2362%
Success Rate:	65.5%	97.9021%	99%

Table 3: Statistical results of the position dispersion at Hold Point for the main cases

Position disp. (km)	Scenario 1-OI	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Metric (worst axis):	17 (Y axis)	17 (Z axis)	17 (Z axis)
Mean:	10.7046	7.7466	4.4589
Std. Deviation:	11.4983	4.7605	2.2293
Success Rate:	81.5%	98.6014%	100%

have a significant effect.

The test results indicate that the GUIBEAR G&N can perform with good results the approach and insertion to the near-rectilinear orbit of the LOP-G, indeed improving on the nominal scenario both in state dispersion and knowledge with a small delta-V cost. In particular: (i) The on-board G&N is capable of performing the insertion manoeuvre in the nominal terms, i.e., by considering fuel-optimality and replacing the ground navigation and *a priori* computed insertion manoeuvre. (ii) Generated trajectories are inherently safe through optimization constraints. (iii) Small manoeuvres do improve the navigation performance to a limited extent. (iv) Letting the on-board optimization take care of the insertion, with the increased delta-V budget associated, is a good option in terms of better use of the manoeuvres for observability. (v) Having an off-pointing of 5 degrees reduces the detection range to a little above 1000 km. This is within the requirements but can be significantly improved with a small pointing error. However, that has thermal and power implications.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The GUIBEAR project has demonstrated that bearings-only navigation for far-range rendezvous is feasible from the point of view of the G&N. The current G&N design improves on the previously analysed approach to the end of the orbit transfer phase of the LAE when rendezvousing the LOP-G at the small added cost of a delta-V expenditure of few meters per second. In particular: (i) the post-insertion dispersion can be about 4x below (3σ) what is achieved with the pre-planned insertion nominally considered in NRO-GNC, and up to 6x below in terms of velocity dispersion; (ii) the navigation estimates have an average accuracy of one order of magnitude better than that achievable without GUIBEAR; and (iii) the propellant consumption required for the good results above is on the order of 5 m/s above that of the pre-planned insertion, and, with as low as 1 m/s in average it is possible to achieve performance improvements, by following Scenario 2. The MIL tests have shown that the GNC software is capable of fulfilling all functions and with adequate performance for the current phase of the activity. The GNC is compliant with the requirements defined at the start of the activity, an aspect that is aided by the optimization-based design of the guidance function since the requirements can be translated into optimization constraints, thus resulting in correct trajectories by design. The sensor models that were used in the real world were relatively simple, mostly consisting of behavioural models of sensors and actuators. The interfaces of these models do not correspond to the interfaces of any real, existing hardware. To further increase the TRL of the GNC, representative

Table 4: Statistical results of the velocity dispersion at Hold Point for the main cases

Velocity disp. (m/s)	Scenario 1-OI	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Worst axis:	Y axis	Y axis	Y axis
Mean:	1.1238	0.19221	0.29872
Std. Deviation:	1.7218	0.16201	0.20381

Table 5: Statistical results of the delta-V consumption for the main cases

Delta-V (m/s)	Scenario 1-PI	Scenario 1-OI	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
	<i>Planned</i>	<i>Extra delta-V compared to the planned insertion</i>		
Mean:	20.4144	-1.4523	1.0893	5.4418
Std. Deviation:	6.7249	1.9717	1.0781	2.3319

interfaces with the sensors and actuators, as well as representative sensor pre-processing functions will need to be added to the GNC. This implies that more representative models of the sensors and actuators will need to be developed and included in the real-world model.

As mentioned throughout the paper, the GUIBEAR activity has been focused on the development of G&N functions for the HERACLES mission scenario with the LAE vehicle. Within the duration of the activity, the HERACLES mission definition has changed due to the programmatic change of the Lunar Gateway. The mission has evolved in 2 different activities: the ESA-EL3 (European Logistic Lunar Lander) activity and the ESA CLTV (Cis-Lunar Transfer Vehicle). At the current time, a sample-return is not being considered for EL3, and therefore the HERACLES assumptions are not currently valid. However, CLTV (Cis-Lunar Transfer Vehicle) will require to dock with the Gateway, and could therefore benefit from the design and the results obtained within the GUIBEAR activity. A dedicated step to adapt the design to the CLTV mission scenario and vehicle has been consequently envisaged as natural continuation of the GUIBEAR activity.

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